

Solid-state magnetic refrigerator based on the demagnetizing effect

C. R. Fernandes,¹ R. Almeida,¹ J. S. Amaral,² J. H. Belo,¹ J. O. Ventura,¹ and D. J. Silva¹

¹*IFIMUP, Departamento de Física e Astronomia, Faculdade de Ciências,
Universidade do Porto, rua do Campo Alegre s/n, 4169-007 Porto, Portugal*

²*Physics Department and CICECO, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal*

(Dated: June 7, 2025)

With population growth, changes in lifestyle and global warming, the demand for ecological and low-energy consumption technologies is rising sharply. Magnetic refrigeration is a promising alternative to conventional refrigeration. However, several factors still impair its performance, thereby delaying commercialization. The use of thermal management elements (such as thermal switches) instead of thermal fluids for heat transfer can avoid some of the main issues arising from conduction/convection, fluid oscillation and mechanical friction. Furthermore, the rotating magnetocaloric effect can effectively solve the problem of the demagnetizing field commonly associated with this technology. Therefore, here we propose and numerically simulate a novel solid-state magnetic refrigerator based on the rotating magnetocaloric effect, generated by the alternated rotation of magnetocaloric material plates under a constant magnetic field. The performance of the proposed device improves with the decrease in the inverse aspect ratio of the magnetocaloric material plates, reaching a maximum no-load temperature span of 2.02 K. The implementation of asymmetric cycles can lead to enhancements of up to 30% in the temperature span, which compensates the use of low-intensity magnetic fields in future applications. This innovative and compact model enables the development of a novel class of magnetic refrigerators based on the rotating magnetocaloric effect.

Keywords: Magnetocaloric effect; Rotating magnetocaloric effect; Demagnetizing-based magnetic refrigerator; Solid-state magnetic refrigeration; Thermal switch

NOMENCLATURE

AMR Active Magnetic Regenerator

HHEX/CHEx Hot/Cold Heat Exchangers

MCE Magnetocaloric Effect

MCM Magnetocaloric Material

MR Magnetic Refrigerator

Greek

δ Plates thickness (mm)

μ_f Dynamic viscosity (Pa · s)

ω Plates width (mm)

ρ Density (kgm⁻³)

Roman

ΔT Temperature span (K)

ΔT_{ad} Adiabatic temperature change (K)

N/N Demagnetizing field tensor/factor (-)

C Specific heat capacity (Jkg⁻¹K⁻¹)

d	Distance between plates (mm)
H	Effective magnetic field (Am ⁻¹)
H_{appl}	Applied magnetic field (Am ⁻¹)
H_d	Demagnetizing field (Am ⁻¹)
k	Thermal conductivity (Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
L	Length (mm)
M	Magnetization (Am ⁻¹)
P	Period of the cycle (s)
T	Temperature (K)
t	Time (s)
T_C	Curie temperature(K)

1. INTRODUCTION

Refrigeration and air-conditioning have become essential in society and, with the constant population increase and lifestyle changes, there has been a fast expansion of these technologies market [1, 2]. In fact, the global commercial refrigeration market was reported to grow 14%, between 2017 and 2021 [2]. Furthermore, it is estimated that the fraction of global electricity consumption associated with refrigeration is approximately 17% [1], which will increase in the next years given the growth of the mentioned market size. Furthermore, refrigeration

technologies typically use hydrofluorocarbons as a working substance, with direct impact on global warming [3]. Magnetic refrigeration emerges as a promising alternative to present technologies as it is an ecological option and allows an energy consumption reduction of approximately 35% [4]. The operation of this technology relies on the magnetocaloric effect (MCE) experienced by the magnetocaloric material (MCM) used as refrigerant. In addition to the MCM, a conventional magnetic refrigerator (MR) also incorporates hot and cold exchangers (HHEX and CHEX), a magnetic field source, and a thermal fluid to enable the heat transfer between components [3, 5].

Despite significant progress [3, 6], this technology still faces numerous challenges that limit its performance and hinder commercialization. Losses related to heat transfer (inefficiencies in conduction and convection), flow dividers, changes in fluid direction, mechanical friction, and degradation caused by the demagnetizing factor are some of the critical aspects that negatively impact the MR performance [7–9]. To overcome issues related to heat transfer, the use of thermal management elements, and in particular thermal switches instead of thermal fluids for heat transfer, has been suggested [7]. The thermal resistance of a thermal switch varies depending on the application/removal of an external stimuli, operating in two states, "on" and "off". When the TS is in the "on"/"off" state, the overall thermal resistance is minimized/maximized, thus maximizing/minimizing heat transfer [10]. The concept of a solid-state magnetic refrigerator was first proposed by Kitanovski *et al.* [7], where the MCM was sandwiched between two layers of heat semiconductors, which were in turn between the HHEX and CHEX. When an external stimulus was applied, e.g. an electric current, one of the semiconductors operated as a thermal conductor and the other as a thermal insulator. The reverse occurred in both layers when the electric current was reduced or removed. Silva *et al.* [11] simulated a similar device, where the MCM was sandwiched between two materials whose thermal conductivity depends on the application and removal of the magnetic field. For the ideal case, the device achieved a temperature span of 2.5 K. Later, Tomc *et al.* [8] simulated a similar device by placing the MCM between two Peltier elements, to evaluate its performance under different conditions. With the Python package *heatrapy*, Silva *et al.* [12] simulated a device with MCM and two TSs whose conductivity varied between 0 and that of copper, reaching a temperature span of 4.59 K. More recently, Klinar *et al.* [13] simulated a more realistic device considering two ferrofluidic thermal switches, which also operate alternately depending on the application/removal of the magnetic field, and achieved a temperature span of 1.12 K. Finally, an experimental demonstration of a solid-state refrigerator was recently reported by Andrade *et al.* [14]. The prototype consists of a MCM (gadolinium) coupled with a single ferrofluidic thermal switch and achieved a temperature span of approximately 2 K.

Multiple methods have been reported to improve the performance of solid-state magnetic refrigerators, including the implementation of asymmetric magnetic field application/removal cycles [14], the gradual movement of the magnetic field [15] and the inclusion of multiple TSs placed between MCM elements [16, 17]. The latter is the most common approach, highlighting the models developed by Olsen *et al.* [16] and subsequently by Utaka *et al.* [17]. In particular, the latter relied on the rotation of MCM elements half-coated with a thermal insulator as switching mechanism. Heat transfer (TS "on") occurs when surfaces with the same thermal conductivity overlap, while thermal insulation (TS "off") is achieved by overlapping surfaces with different thermal conductivities.

Another challenge in magnetic refrigeration is the demagnetizing effect, which can considerably lower the internal magnetic field of the MCM upon magnetic field application [18–20]. One potential solution is implementing the rotating magnetocaloric effect (RMCE), which consists of an adiabatic temperature change generated by a variation in the orientation of the applied magnetic field [21–23]. Recently, the authors of the present work proposed and optimized a device based on the RMCE. This proof-of-concept has the structure of a conventional MR (using fluids instead of TSs) and operates using a Brayton-based cycle, reaching a temperature span of 7.27 K after optimization [24]. Thus, in this work, we simulated the performance of a novel solid-state magnetic refrigerator based on RMCE, consisting of two TSs. This type of device is more compact since it can operate with a simple permanent magnet field source (e.g., a Halbach cylinder) and does not require any fluid or pistons for fluid movement. After validation, the proposed solid-state device was computed considering the application of a low magnetic field (0.4 T) and the impact of using asymmetric cycles.

2. PROPOSED SOLID-STATE MAGNETIC REFRIGERATOR

The proposed model design incorporates the AMR, CHEX and HHEX, in alignment with the conventional MR [3, 6, 25, 26]. However, instead of the thermal fluid, it uses thermal switches for the heat transfer processes. We considered arrangements of parallel plates, as shown in Fig. 1, to harness the demagnetizing effect resulting from the application of a constant magnetic field. The effective magnetic field of the MCM (\mathbf{H}) is described by the sum of the applied (\mathbf{H}_{appl}) and demagnetizing fields (\mathbf{H}_{d}):

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} + \mathbf{H}_{\text{d}}. \quad (1)$$

The demagnetizing field is generated when the external magnetic field is applied to the MCM, reducing the total internal magnetic field:

TABLE I. Material properties of the Gd, Copper and TSs used in the simulations.

	k [W · m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	C_P [Jkg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	ρ [kgm ⁻³]
Gd	10.5	-	7900
Copper and TS_{ON}	401	385	8933
TS_{OFF}	0.01	385	8933

$$\mathbf{H}_d = -\mathbb{N} \cdot \mathbf{M}. \quad (2)$$

Here, \mathbb{N} is the demagnetizing field tensor that depends only on the geometry, and \mathbf{M} is its magnetization [19, 27]. Thus, the RMCE is characterized by an adiabatic temperature change in the MCM, which occurs after rotating the magnetic field source while keeping the MCM static, or vice-versa [23, 24]. As described in Ref. [24], the flux density of the applied magnetic field remains constant during the entire device operation ($B_{appl} = \mu_0 \cdot H_{appl} = 1$ T), only changing its direction. The demagnetizing effect is predominant when H_{appl} is applied along the thickness of the plates ($H_{appl} \parallel \delta$), i.e., the internal magnetic field intensity is lower than the one obtained when H_{appl} is parallel to the length ($H_{appl} \parallel L_{MCM}$).

As can be seen in Fig. 1(a), the device consists of two arrangements of Gd parallel plates (MCM1 and MCM2), perpendicular to each other and separated by one TS. In this system, each TS is between two copper discs. These two arrays are positioned between the HHEX (MCM1 on the left) and the CHEX (MCM2 on the right), both made of copper. The HHEX is fixed at 293 K. Between the array of parallel plates (MCM2) and the CHEX on the right, there is one TS. The working principle of the used TS is based on the work developed by Utaka *et al.* [17], where the switching mechanism is performed by rotating the elements of the MCM, with the interface half coated in a low-thermal conductivity material. Nevertheless, in this case, the thermal switch consists of two discs, each with one half made of insulating material and the other half made of copper. Each arrangement of parallel plates will rotate together with a copper disc and half of the TS, as shown in Fig. 1(b). When the materials of the TSs with equal/different thermal conductivities overlap, there is heat transfer/insulation ("on"/"off" state). For simplicity, we modeled an ideal case in which the thermal conductivity in the "on" state is equal to that of copper, while in the "off" state there is perfect thermal insulation (Table I).

The refrigeration cycle is divided into two stages (Figs. 1(b) and (c)). Initially, in the first half of the cycle (1), the magnetic field is applied parallel to the length of the MCM1 plates and along the thickness of the MCM2 plates. This leads to the increase of the temperature of MCM1 and decrease of that of MCM2. During the second half of the cycle (1 \rightarrow 2), MCM1 and MCM2 rotate 90°, together with the respective copper discs and the

TABLE II. Width, thickness and inverse aspect ratio of the used Gd plates.

δ [mm]	ω [mm]	δ/ω
0.5	20	0.03
1	10	0.1
1.25	8	0.16
1.6	6.25	0.26
2	5	0.4
2.5	4	0.63
3.125	3.2	0.98

half of the adjacent TS. This inverts the initial temperature increase/decrease behavior. As MCM1 (MCM2) switches to a configuration that reduces (maximizes) the demagnetizing field, the internal magnetic field increases (decreases), resulting in a temperature rise (decline). In the following stage (2 \rightarrow 1), the elements rotate 90° again, and the inverse occurs, leading to a temperature drop/rise in MCM1/MCM2. This process occurs periodically, gradually resulting in a substantial CHEX temperature span.

Seven Gd plates with different widths (ω) and thicknesses (δ) were considered to evaluate the refrigerator performance while keeping their volume and length constant at 200 mm³ and 20 mm, respectively. This way, we always use the same mass and volume of MCM, varying only the inverse aspect ratio (δ/ω) of the plate. Additionally, the contact area between each plate and the copper disk is always 10 mm². Table II contains the dimensions of the seven plates considered.

Mathematical description and numerical model

A 1D model was used to evaluate the performance of the system previously described (Fig. 2(a)). The stack of materials $HHEX/MCM1/Cu/TS1/Cu/MCM2/Cu/TS1/Cu/MCM2/CHEX$ was considered to solve the problem. Similarly to the approach described in Ref. [10], the model was implemented using the Python package heatrapy (v1.0.3), which is suitable to model heat transfer processes involving thermal switches [10, 14] and magnetocaloric systems [12, 28, 29]. We chose an implicit method due to the stability advantage that it provides over an explicit one. Given that the thermal conductivity varies along the x-axis in the stack of materials, our choice relied on the x-dependent thermal conductivity implicit method '*implicit.k(x)*'. The 1D heat equation is then solved:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density of the material, C_p its specific heat under constant pressure, k its thermal conductivity and

FIG. 1. (a) 2D representation of the proposed refrigerator; the red/blue arrow describes the temperature increase/decrease, while the orange one indicates the direction of heat transfer. (b) Rotation of the two sets of rotating elements - MCM1/2, adjacent copper disk, and half of the TS - during the two step refrigeration process. (c) Temperature variation of MCM1 and MCM2 over time upon the change in direction of the magnetic field, which can be applied parallel or perpendicular to the plates.

T the temperature. Then, the Crank-Nicolson method was applied to Eq. 3, resulting in:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\gamma + k_{i+1}^{n+1} + 2k_i^{n+1} + k_{i-1}^{n+1}) T_i^{n+1} - \\ & (k_{i+1}^{n+1} + k_i^{n+1}) T_{i+1}^{n+1} - (k_{i-1}^{n+1} + k_i^{n+1}) T_{i-1}^{n+1} = \\ & (\gamma - k_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2k_i^{n+1} - k_{i-1}^{n+1}) T_i^n + \\ & (k_{i+1}^{n+1} + k_i^{n+1}) T_{i+1}^n + (k_{i-1}^{n+1} + k_i^{n+1}) T_{i-1}^n, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, i and n are the space and time index, Δx and Δt are the space and time steps, and

$$\gamma = \frac{4\Delta x^2 \rho_i^{n+1} C_i^{n+1}}{\Delta t}. \quad (5)$$

The discrete temperature change step method was considered to compute the application/removal of the magnetic field, given its simplicity and fast computation [12, 30]. Therefore, the considered MCM temperature change between two consecutive instants was:

$$T_i^{n+1} = T_i^n \pm \Delta T_{ad}^\pm(T_i^n), \quad (6)$$

where ΔT_{ad} is the adiabatic temperature change when the magnetic field is applied or removed. When the magnetic field is applied (removed) this change is positive (negative), which results in an increment (decrement) of ΔT_{ad} in the MCM temperature, denoted by the + (-) sign.

Figure 2(a) shows the discretization of the proposed refrigeration process, where Δx denotes the time step and k_{OFF} and k_{ON} the thermal conductivity of the TSs in the "off" and "on" states, respectively. The proposed system was compared with a simpler one, where the MCM1 and MCM2 plates always have the same orientation, and only the applied magnetic field changes its direction, with the goal of evaluating the advantages of using the alternating rotation mechanism. In contrast to the system with the alternating rotation mechanism, the latter system completely rotates in both stages of the cycle, as described in

FIG. 2. 1D discretization of (a) the proposed refrigeration process and (b) simpler system without TSs and rotating elements for comparison.

Fig. 2(b). Furthermore, the TSs were replaced by copper, which implies that there is always heat transfer between all components. The thermal properties of the used materials can be found in Table I. For the discretization depicted in Fig. 2(a), we defined $L_{MCM1} = L_{MCM2} = 20$ mm, $L_{CHEX} = L_{HHEX} = 15$ mm, $L_{Cu} = L_{TS} = 2$ mm, and the space step is defined as $\Delta x = 0.001$ m. We performed a convergence study using the simplest system (Fig. 2(b)), as fully described in the *Supporting Information*, to determine the most suitable time step Δt . Subsequently, we selected $\Delta t = 0.01$ s.

4. RESULTS

The periodic rotating mechanism was validated as described in the *Supporting Information*. The temperature change of the system with the alternating rotation mechanism was computed, considering the inverse aspect ratios from Table II. To better understand the system's performance, the CHEX temperature was measured to then evaluate the temperature span of the system, de-

fined as:

$$\Delta T = T_{HHEX} - T_{CHEX}. \quad (7)$$

Here, T_{HHEX} is fixed at 293 K and is equal to the initial temperature. The period P of the cycle ranges between 10 and 400 seconds. Figure 3(a) shows the temperature span as a function of the period for the evaluated inverse aspect ratios. For a given period, the temperature span rises with the inverse aspect ratio reduction. This occurs due to the growing difference between demagnetizing factors N_δ and N_ω , as well as the difference between generated demagnetizing fields when the plates are perpendicular and parallel to the applied magnetic field. Consequently, the difference between the effective magnetic fields in the MCM will also rise, resulting in a larger adiabatic temperature change that leads to an enhanced temperature span. For each inverse aspect ratio, the temperature span has a maximum ΔT_{max} that ranges between $P = 50$ and 70 s ($P(\delta/\omega = 0.03) = P(\delta/\omega = 0.1) = 50$ s, $P(\delta/\omega = 0.16) = P(\delta/\omega = 0.26) = P(\delta/\omega = 0.4) = 60$ s and $P(\delta/\omega = 0.63) = P(\delta/\omega = 0.976563) = 70$ s).

FIG. 3. (a) Temperature span for different inverse aspect ratios as a function of the cycle period. (b) Temperature variation of the CHEX over time for the best performance of each inverse aspect ratio.

Figure 3(b) shows the CHEX temperature variation as a function of time for each one of the inverse aspect ratios by considering the period where the temperature span is maximum. Once again, the systems with plates with smaller inverse aspect ratio present a larger ΔT , highlighting a maximum ΔT of 2.02 K for $\delta/\omega = 0.03$. The maximum value of ΔT for each inverse aspect ratio drops sharply with its growth (Fig. 4(a)). Furthermore, Fig. 4(a) shows that the maximum ΔT obtained for each of the inverse aspect ratios is very close to the respective peaks of the ΔT_{ad} curves. Thus, the maximum ΔT as a function of the ΔT_{ad} peak for the corresponding δ/ω can be approximated by the linear fit $\Delta T_{max}(\Delta T_{ad}) = 1.03 \cdot \Delta T_{ad} - 0.03$. This occurs because the optimization was performed under ideal conditions. However, since the main goal of this work was to present a new concept and simulate it with thermal switches, we considered a change

FIG. 4. (a) Maximum temperature span as a function of the adiabatic temperature change maximum, in green, and as a function of the inverse aspect ratio, in blue. (b) Comparison between the system with and without TSs. Representation of the maximum and minimum temperature span for the system without TSs.

of 100%. Nevertheless, in the literature, one can find thermal switches that can achieve changes up to $\sim 70\%$ [31].

To better understand the advantage of using the system with the alternating rotation mechanism, simulations of a simpler design, where the MCM1 and MCM2 plates always have the same direction and no TSs, were performed (Fig. 4(b)). The comparison was done for $\delta/\omega = 0.03$. It is observed that, for the latter system, the temperature span reduces with the period. A maximum $\Delta T = 1.01$ K was found for a refrigeration cycle with $P = 10$ s, and for the same period of 50 s, a reduction of 76.73% was observed. Other metrics such as cooling power ($\dot{Q}_c = \frac{mC_p(T_{final} - T_{initial})}{\Delta t}$) and coefficient of performance ($COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_c}{\dot{Q}_h - \dot{Q}_c}$) can be used to establish a better comparison between the performance of the two systems for $P = 50$ s [13, 14, 32]. A maximum cooling capacity per unit area of 147.11 Wm^{-2} and a COP of 1.75

FIG. 5. Comparison between the temperature span obtained for $\delta/\omega = 0.03$ at 0.4 T and some selected δ/ω at 1 T. Percentage decrease in the temperature span when the magnetic field intensity is reduced by 60% (green).

were obtained for the system with the alternating rotation mechanism. A significant reduction in performance was observed for the system without thermal switches, with a maximum cooling capacity per unit area of 40.2 Wm^{-2} and a COP of 0.11. Another drawback of the system without TSs is the significant temperature oscillations that occur as the cycling period increases (Fig. S4). We also verified that, for large periods, the system does not refrigerate, displaying a negative temperature span. Thus, a reduction above $\sim 76\%$ of the minimum temperature span was obtained when compared to the minimum obtained by the previous system. Since the temperature span declines as δ/ω grows, the performance of the simpler system worsens for the remaining plates with $\delta/\omega > 0.03$, and there is no refrigeration in some cases.

Using low-intensity magnetic fields is a possibility in future rotating MCE refrigerators. Hence, we lowered the magnetic field intensity to 0.4 T, since previous studies have shown that this adjustment does not result in a drastic reduction of the adiabatic temperature change peak. Once again, the inverse aspect ratio $\delta/\omega = 0.03$ was selected, since it provided the best results regarding the temperature span [23]. The maximum adiabatic temperature change dropped from 1.96 K to 1.22 K, representing a decrease of approximately 38%. For $\delta/\omega = 0.03$ at 0.4 T, a maximum temperature span of 1.31 K was obtained for $P = 30$ s (Fig. 5). Throughout the periods studied, the temperature span reduction ranged from 33.6 to 38%, generally increasing with the period. The performance of the refrigerator with $\delta/\omega = 0.03$ at 0.4 T surpassed that of $\delta/\omega = 0.16$ at 1 T for $P=10$ and 20 s and $\delta/\omega > 0.16$ at 1 T.

Andrade *et al.* [14] proved that asymmetric cycles can improve the performance of a solid-state MR. Through simulations, the authors showed that the temperature span can be enhanced by 20% using symmetrical cycles

as initial reference. In these cycles, the time of application/removal of the magnetic field is different, i.e., it can be longer than the time when it is not applied, or vice-versa. To understand the implementation of asymmetric cycles in a conventional MR, the parameter $\chi = \frac{P^{on}}{P}$, which represents the time fraction of the total period during which the magnetic field is applied (P^{on}) was previously considered [14]. For the solid-state MR based on the demagnetizing effect, we define a similar quantity:

$$\chi = \frac{P^{MCM1}}{P}, \quad (8)$$

where P^{MCM1} is the fraction of the period during which the magnetic field is applied parallel to the set MCM1 and perpendicular to the set MCM2. At the same time, TS1 is deactivated, while TS2 is activated. Contrarily, for the remaining period, $P^{MCM2} (= P - P^{MCM1})$, the magnetic field is applied parallel to set MCM2 and perpendicular to set MCM1. During this time frame, TS1 is activated and TS2 deactivated. For clarity, the quantity χ will be referred to as the asymmetric time fraction.

Figure 6 illustrates the findings on the impact of implementing asymmetric cycles. For both 1 and 0.4 T, it is possible to observe that, for periods of 10 s or longer, the optimum temperature span occurs for $\chi \geq 0.6$ and χ tends to grow with the cycle period (Figs. 6(a) and (b)). Examining the results from the initial symmetric cycle with $B_{appl} = 1$ T, a significant improvement in the temperature span can be observed when asymmetric cycles are employed. On the one hand, when a magnetic field of 1 T is applied, there are improvements of 6.1, 15.51, 22.41, and 31.91% for $P = 10, 50, 100,$ and 200 s, respectively. On the other hand, after reducing the applied magnetic field to 0.4 T, improvements of 0.51, 5.14, 17.67, and 29.1% are observed for $P = 10, 50, 100,$ and 200 s, respectively (compared to the initial symmetric cycle with $B_{appl} = 0.4$ T). Figures 6(c) and (d) show the best results obtained using asymmetric cycles for 1 and 0.4 T. Note that the black lines represent the best temperature span when using the original symmetric cycles. For 1 T, the best result is 2.37 K, while for $B_{appl} = 0.4$ T the best temperature span is 1.43 K, both for $P = 100$ s and $\chi = 0.9$. The latter represents a reduction of only 29% regarding the best result using the original symmetric cycles and an applied field of 1 T. These outcomes reveal that a significant reduction of the magnetic field does not drastically reduce the temperature span, and that this decline can even be compensated by implementing asymmetric cycles.

Finally, although the maximum obtained temperature span is not as large as the values found in the literature for common solid-state magnetic refrigerators, it is close to the device computed by Silva *et al.* [11] (2.5 K), and is larger than that found in the device simulated by Klinar *et al.* [13] (1.12 K). Nevertheless, a slightly lower temperature span would be expected if more realistic TSs had been considered in our simulations. The

FIG. 6. Temperature span as function of asymmetric time fraction for (a) $B_{\text{appl}} = 1$ and (b) 0.4 T. Temperature evolution for the periods and respective χ with best temperature span for (c) $B_{\text{appl}} = 1 \text{ T}$ and (d) 0.4 T.

COP and cooling capacity are lower than those reported for prototypes operating conventional MCE [33], which is expected, since conventional MCE provides a larger adiabatic temperature change.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a novel solid-state magnetic refrigerator based on the demagnetizing effect. The rotating magnetocaloric effect was employed in two sets of rotating elements (gadolinium plates, copper plate, and half of the thermal switch), inducing different adiabatic temperature changes. The temperature span reduces with the inverse aspect ratio of the plate, considering the same amount of magnetocaloric material. Moreover, for different inverse aspect ratios, different maximum temperature spans occur for cycles with periods ranging between 50

and 70 s. A maximum temperature span of 2.02 K was obtained for an inverse aspect ratio of 0.03 and a period of 50 s. For the same period, a maximum cooling capacity per unit area of 147.11 Wm^{-2} and a COP of 1.75 were obtained. The alternating rotation mechanism was shown to offer significant advantages over the simple rotation of the entire system (maximum temperature span of 1.01 K), since it resulted in a 99% enhancement of the temperature span.

We also evaluated the performance for the inverse aspect ratio that provided the largest temperature span under a magnetic field of 0.4 T, revealing a reduction of approximately 35% in the maximum temperature span. At 0.4 T, the device's performance for the smallest inverse aspect ratio surpassed the performance of the four largest inverse aspect ratios considered, showing the possibility of applying magnetic field sources with less magnetic material, which may lower the overall cost of the

refrigerator.

Simulations using asymmetric cycles were performed, resulting in improved refrigerator performance for magnetic fields of 1 and 0.4 T, specifically in the case of the inverse aspect ratio that provided the largest temperature span in the previous simulations. Compared to symmetric cycles, the application of asymmetric cycles allowed enhancements of up to 30% in the temperature span. These results reveal that it will be possible to select magnetic field sources that generate a lower magnetic field without significantly compromising the refrigerator's performance.

Finally, the system performance can be enhanced by increasing its size and dimensions by adding more MCMs and TSs. However, adding more components will raise the total cost of the refrigerator. Even if the magnetic field magnitude remains the same, the magnetic field source must be larger to surround all new elements and ensure that the magnetic field is applied uniformly, which makes the system even more expensive. From the practical point of view, issues such as heat generation due to friction from the rotating discs may emerge, becoming more significant as the system is scaled. Additionally, more power will be required to operate the motor responsible for the rotating components. The operation will also become more complex, as it must synchronize the alternated rotation of a larger number of elements. Future work could investigate hybrid systems that combine magnetocaloric refrigeration with other caloric technologies, such as elastocaloric, electrocaloric, or barocaloric effects. These multimodal approaches may offer complementary advantages in terms of operating conditions or response times. Such integration could pave the way for more adaptable and efficient solid-state cooling systems, optimized for specific applications or variable environmental conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by FEDER funds through the COMPETE 2020 Programme and National Funds through FCT – Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology under projects UID/NAN/50024/2019, PTDC/EME-SIS/31575/2017-POCI-01-0145-FEDER-031575 and PTDC/EME-TED/3099/2020. D. J. S. acknowledges his contract DL57/2016 reference SFRH-BPD-90571/2012. This work was developed within the scope of the project CICECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials, UIDB/50011/2020, UIDP/50011/2020 & LA/P/0006/2020, financed by national funds through the FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme through the European Innovation Council under the grant agreement No. 101161135 – MAGCCINE.

FIG. S1. Convergence study: temperature span as a function of time step.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Convergence study

Let us consider the system without TSs. To evaluate the accuracy of the chosen time step, all parameters were fixed while the time step, Δt , was varied between 10^{-4} and 10. We defined $\Delta x = 0.001$ m, $\delta/\omega = 0.03$ and $P = 50$ s. Figure S1 shows the evolution of ΔT with Δt . The ΔT values display an oscillatory and unstable behavior with the increase of Δt due to approximation errors [34]. One can observe the convergence of ΔT to approximately 0.52 K as Δt decreases, for $\Delta t < 0.02$ s. To ensure fast simulations and the accuracy of the simulated results, we selected $\Delta t = 0.01$ s. Typically, as Δt decreases, a divergence in results relative to the stable minimum can be observed, due to the effect of roundoff errors (the error accumulates as calculations are performed on the computer) [10, 30]. However, the range of the analyzed Δt does not include small enough values to detect the occurrence of this phenomenon.

Validation

The rotation of the different elements is crucial for the operation of the proposed system. Therefore, validating the rotation of the MCM element under a constant magnetic field and, consequently, the RMCE is particularly important. For this reason, a setup with only a small Gd sample and without thermal switches was used. The temperature change of the sample exposed to a periodically rotating magnetic field of constant magnitude, generated by a Halbach cylinder (Fig. S2(a)), was experimentally measured. The sample consisted of two identical halves sandwiched together, with the temper-

FIG. S2. (a) Halbach cylinder used to generate the rotating magnetic field. (b) Experimental setup used to validate the rotation of the Gd sample. (c) Sample fixed with paper and GE varnish on the copper sample holder. Experimental setup used to validate the rotation of the Gd sample (c) showing the sample. (d) The Halbach cylinder is placed on a non-magnetic wooden support, which is on an acrylic rotating platform to enable the rotation required to induce the RMCE.

ature sensor (type-K thermocouple) tip positioned between them (Fig. S2(b)). The sample was measured within a vacuum atmosphere in a cryostat for accurate temperature control (Fig. S2(c) and (d)). To slow down thermal exchange with the copper sample holder, two layers of paper, glued with GE varnish ($k = 0.44 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, $\rho = 880 \text{ kgm}^{-3}$ and $C_P = 1435.2 \text{ Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ [31]), are placed between the sample and sample holder. The two halves have dimensions of $0.04 \times 4.6 \times 7 \text{ mm}^3$. Thus, this system can be simulated by only considering a stack of *Paper/GE – Varnish/Gd/Gd*. The dimensions used for the computations were not the real ones because the materials used were very thin. Since we are performing a validation, we should use the same grid parameters throughout the rest of the work, also noting that, adjusting new space and time steps would require performing another convergence study. Moreover, both steps would have very small dimensions, and the computation time would be significantly increased. To obtain the final re-

sults, it is necessary to apply a scaling factor for conversion, reducing the scale by approximately 100 times. Then, we defined $L_{paper} = 11 \text{ mm}$, $L_{GE-Varnish} = 4 \text{ mm}$ and $L_{Gd} = 4 \text{ mm}$. The temperature at the ends of the stack was fixed at 290.38 K , since its experimental temperature remained constant due to the cryostat. The system was discretized according to the previously specified values ($\Delta x = 1 \text{ mm}$ and $\Delta t = 0.01 \text{ s}$).

After waiting 31 s, 9 cycles with a period of 10 s were performed. The scaling factor given by $0.58 \cdot (T_{Gd} - 290.38)$ was subtracted from the obtained results. The full magnetocaloric response of the sample in this setup is published in Ref. [35] (setup A). Figure S3 shows

FIG. S3. Validation of the periodic rotation of two small Gd samples.

the similarity between the experimental and simulated results, thus validating the system.

Systems with and without Thermal Switches

Figures S4(a) and (b) show the temperature evolution for systems with and without TSs, respectively, considering three distinct periods. Temperature oscillations increase is more noticeable for the system without TSs.

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FIG. S4. Temperature over time for systems (a) with and (b) without TSs.

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